

TYPES OF ASSIMILATION IN PHONETICS AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN SPEAKING

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Annotation:

The given article depicts the types of assimilation in phonetics of the English language. The theory of assimilation as well as the importance of it in communicating.

This study aims to help English learners understand English speech and have the ability to produce a natural speech too.

Key words: Assimilation, phonetics, speaking, connected speech, sound.

Introduction

Assimilation is an impact of a certain sound to its next coming sound. Assimilation is the process when two neighbouring sounds blend into one single sound or become very similar to one another. Assimilation normally takes place in everyday conversations however more than often it is common in fast spoken language. In some situations, assimilation makes a certain sound to differ from the usual pronunciation when it is in isolation, such as the prefix in- of English input pronounced with phonetic [m] instead of [n]. In other cases, assimilation is canonical since a word or phrase, particularly if it has a standard spelling: implosion pronounced with [m], composed of in- + -plosion (as in explosion).

Although the assimilation of the n of in- to the next standing consonant in the above mentioned examples is inherited from Latin, English words that are native also

enough. In a fast everyday conversation native speakers of English have a tendency to pronounce “ten bucks” as “tembucks”, and in anticipation of the voiceless “s” in a word “son” the final consonant of “his” in “his son” is not as fully voiced as the “s” in “his daughter”, where it clearly is [1]. Both synchronic and diachronic assimilation, or changes in historical sound patterns, can occur simultaneously in a language [2].

Assimilation in phonetics

A subfield of linguistics called phonology investigates the structure and interaction of speech sounds [3]. In connected speech, a word's pronunciation will vary depending on the words that are spoken around it. Because each phoneme has an effect on the pronunciation of a sound, it can alter. It is known as assimilation. One of the features of connected speech is assimilation. The principle of assimilation states that speaking quickly with English native speakers requires sound alterations.

The term assimilation in phonetics. Assimilation is the process by which a sound is impacted by and melds with its surroundings. As a result, the pronunciation can change based on the placement of particular letters inside various words. Typically, this is done to make pronouncing words easier, especially when they are said fast. The term "handbag" serves as an illustration. Native speakers rarely pronounce each letter clearly since it disrupts the flow of speech and is more challenging when speaking quickly. They would probably pronounce it as /haembg/ instead (hambag).

Types of assimilation

Assimilation is the process of changing a speech sound so that it more closely resembles its neighbors. The technique of simplifying involves influencing a spoken sound to make it more similar to the noises around it. Progressive assimilation, regressive assimilation, and reciprocal assimilation are the three types of assimilation.

Progressive Assimilation

According to Peter Roach, when two words are merged, assimilation can occur if the first word has a single final consonant (which we'll refer to as Cf: Consonant final) and the second word has a single initial consonant (which we will call Ci: Consonant

initial). It is referred to as progressive assimilation when Ci alters to resemble Cf in some aspect.

This type happens when segment A (first) has an impact on segment B in the sequence of segments AB (second). We can categorize A as an assimilator and B as being absorbed. The word "got" has an alveolar /t/ at the end, whereas the word "them" has an interdental /d/. When these two sounds are merged to form the word "get them," the interdental /d/ is frequently pronounced like the sound before it, "t," which is the example. Power flows from left to right.

Regressive Assimilation

Regressive assimilation is most likely to move toward a simpler consonant that causes less airflow restriction, according to Peter Roach. Hence, it is feasible to come across instances where a final plosive changes into a fricative or a nasal, but it is quite rare that a final fricative or nasal would change into a final plosive.

Example: "That side," remarked Daes, "good night."

The sound that is digested produces a new sound in regressive. When the final sound of the word before it sounds identical to the first word, this is known as regression assimilation. The sound of "that page" becomes "dt ped" in the example, where the alveolar /t/ transforms to a /p/ because the second word, page, starts with a /p/. When the final consonant affects the first, it occurs.

Reciprocal Assimilation

When the sequences of segments AB and B exert effect on segments A and B, respectively, this is known as reciprocal assimilation. A and B are assimilators, then. When two sounds merge to create a new sound, this happens. Reciprocal is referred to as coalescent in other contexts. When a sound meets the letter /y/, coalescence occurs. For instance, "they called you" (ei ka:ld ju) becomes "they called you" (ei ka: ldu:) when the /d/ and /y/ sounds are combined. The two phonemes interact with one another to create a new sound. Dental sound /d/ meets /y/ and /j/ to create the new sound /d/.

Further categorized into two forms is reciprocal assimilation. As follows:

1. Reciprocal Assimilation without Coaling

This assimilation happens when the two sounds mutually impact one another. As a result, both sounds gain some feature mutually, but they still maintain a fair amount of autonomy.

2. The second is coalescent reciprocal assimilation

During a process known as segmentation, a new sound (referred to as assimilation) is created. Samples of the term "get you" /t/ ↔ /j/ → /tʃ/

Conclusion

Each language in the world has different pieces and similarities to other languages, making up the numerous parts that make up language. Phonetics allows for the categorization and study of the sounds that make up a language. To identify the distinctive and comparable sounds in different languages, phonetics might be useful. The study of phonetics can aid in the identification of dialects, accents, and other linguistic phenomena.

Reference

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